

The ODISSEI Portal: Linking Survey and Administrative Data

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ARTICLE HISTORY

Compiled December 1, 2020

ABSTRACT

The ODISSEI Portal will combine metadata from a wide variety of social science research data providers into a single interface, allow advanced semantic queries to support findability, and facilitate data access. In particular, the Portal will include metadata of (a) the microdata catalogue from Statistics Netherlands, and (b) survey datasets collected by ODISSEI member organizations in the Netherlands. Aligning the metadata from these sources is the primary challenge of this project. The project will ultimately develop a metadata ingestion pipeline to make sure that the Portal can be maintained and kept up to date. This pipeline will convert the metadata of the source surveys to the CESSDA Metadata Model (CMM) used in the portal. The ODISSEI Portal will extend and improve search functionality by using semantic queries which will enable broader probabilistic matching over an enriched knowledge graph representation of the metadata catalogue. This incorporates the context of specific terms which are crucial in social research. By using rich and extensible data structures developed within the linked data community, ODISSEI will develop the relatively flat metadata catalogue in use today into a highly interlinked and graph-based structure needed to conduct advanced semantic searches.

KEYWORDS

Metadata; Administrative Data; Semantic Search; Survey Data; DDI

1. Introduction

ODISSEI (Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations) is the Dutch national research infrastructure for the social sciences in the Netherlands. It is a collaboration between 40 member organizations including all social science faculties in the Netherlands, Statistics Netherlands (CBS), several institutes of the Dutch Royal Academy of Sciences, public research agencies and the national data archive, Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS). ODISSEI aims to provide researchers with the necessary data, expertise and resources to conduct groundbreaking research. ODISSEI includes diverse data that can be linked at the individual level with administrative data from CBS. For example, longitudinal surveys which track

how health or political attitudes change over time can be linked to administrative data from CBS on income or educational history of the respondent. These linkages are done in a secure environment under the control of CBS with the utmost regard for data security through the five safes framework (Desai et al. 2016). These individual level linkages allow for extraordinary and unprecedented insights into social behaviour.

In order to optimally reuse the data, the datasets should be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) (Wilkinson et al. 2016). To achieve this, ODISSEI is developing the ODISSEI Portal which will allow researchers to find valuable data and linkages across ODISSEI member organizations. The ODISSEI Portal will particularly improve the findability and accessibility of important social science datasets, through three components:

- (1) Collating high-quality metadata from ODISSEI member organisation datasets and making them searchable in the ODISSEI Portal interface.
- (2) Advanced search functionality will allow for variable-level semantic queries over a metadata model. This component will be integrated into the Portal interface.
- (3) A system that allows data providers to manage access requests based on the affiliation of the researcher and the purpose and/or type of analysis.

In this paper we outline the design considerations of the ODISSEI Portal and specifically the technical challenges involved in mapping and linking the metadata structures of the two largest components of the ODISSEI data catalogue which are derived from administrative data provided by CBS and the large scale survey data that is collected by various groups of social scientists across the country. We do this through a clear and simple use case that is common within ODISSEI. We then detail the existing standards used across ODISSEI member organizations and datasets and how the ODISSEI Portal team intends to integrate these within a single metadata model. We also outline how linkages across the datasets are identified, common vocabularies and ontologies that are used and how these can be enhanced through semantic search at the variable level.

2. A use case for the ODISSEI Portal

The ODISSEI Portal evolved out of ODISSEI’s wider program of work in promoting access to dutch social science research infrastructures. ODISSEI consists of a large number of diverse data providers and it is difficult to navigate the full range of this data using existing data catalogues. To extrapolate on common findability problems encountered by users of ODISSEI, this section outlines a standard use case involving two of ODISSEI’s most prominent data providers. We start by introducing the data providers and their current metadata documentation practices. We then proceed to discuss common challenges faced by researchers in exploring and interrogating the metadata of both infrastructures, particularly in combination.

2.1. CBS microdata

CBS provide authorised researchers with access to pseudonymized, individual level, administrative data in a secure remote access research environment. This facility has been in operation for almost 15 years and allows verified researchers to conduct analysis using data from CBS. The remote access environment typically processes hundreds

of projects per year. The data are exceptionally powerful for several reasons. Firstly, it provides data on the whole population and the ability to target small and often hard to reach sub-populations. Secondly, the data are diverse and generally of very high quality as they are provided by various organizations and governmental bodies across the country. Finally, the statistical system within CBS applies its own persistent identifiers across a wide range of entities including individuals, schools, companies, neighbourhoods, hospitals etc. This provides scope for far deeper and more complex linkage than is typical in traditional social science research. ODISSEI currently provides grants to individual researchers to access the CBS microlevel data free of charge and to conduct research projects. It also offers all member organizations discounted access to the data. ODISSEI also provides secure HPC environments to analyze this data given the additional complexity that the CBS microdata captures (Scheerman et al. 2020).

The CBS data are archived at CBS and can only be accessed through its secure remote environment. Whilst internal operations at CBS make use of a metadata discovery system, this is designed around a Generic Statistical Business Process Model (GSPBM) that is focused on data dissemination appropriate for the primary functions of a statistical office. These primary functions include servicing government ministries and publishing aggregated data but do not include providing microdata to researchers. That is to say that the metadata system used within CBS has not been designed to account for external researchers accessing the data via a secure remote access environment. This is understandable given the central function of CBS as a provider of statistics to government and the general public.

The possibilities for researchers to find specific CBS microdata are limited given that the automated data documentation process within CBS and the design of data management operations does not account for researchers using micro level data. CBS published data products are aggregate level data products and are documented in such a way that reflects that. However, the remote access environment at CBS allows for researchers to access CBS data at the micro level, before it is aggregated. These microdata are exceptionally powerful for scientific research and represents a rich source of information on a wide range of subjects. Yet at this stage of data processing, the metadata associated with the data are an internal standard used by CBS and designed to facilitate the production of aggregate level statistics rather than enabling someone to explore the metadata at the micro level for research purposes.

Currently researchers looking to explore the metadata for the CBS microdata have access to the data via the CBS Microdata Catalogue ¹. This catalogue documents the approximately 436 data files that are available for use in the CBS secure remote access environment. The documentation is in the form of PDF documents which are downloadable via the CBS website. This provides a description of the dataset, it's source and quality, as well as variable level information ². The documentation is only available in Dutch.

The metadata which documents the microdata that are available via the secure remote environment are derived from the internal CBS metadata catalogue. The transfer of metadata from CBS internal data systems to the remote access environment has some limitations. It involves a process that limits the functionality of the resulting catalogue that researchers use to explore data that is available to them.

¹<https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/onze-diensten/maatwerk-en-microdata/microdata-zelf-onderzoek-doen/catalogus-microdata>

²for an example see (in Dutch only): <https://www.cbs.nl/-/media/cbs-op-maat/microdatabestanden/documents/2020/17/gbaverbintenissenmassatab.pdf>

Firstly, not all CBS microdata files are available to researchers in the remote access environment and there is therefore a manual process which identifies which files can be extracted from the core CBS data lake and deposited in the remote access environment. This prevents the use of the internal CBS microdata catalogue for use by researchers.

Secondly, the extraction leads to a decoupling of versioning within the CBS data lake and data that are available in the remote access environment. Changes made to either the data files or the metadata within CBS would not be reflected in the files in the remote access environment.

Finally, adaptations may be required to specific files or variables as part of making the data available for use which render the metadata inaccurate or incomplete for research purposes. The metadata within CBS Microdata Services is therefore not easily searchable or easily integrated with other metadata sources.

2.2. *The LISS panel*

The second data provider discussed here is the LISS panel. The LISS panel is a longitudinal online representative panel of a random sample of 6,000 Dutch Households (Scherpenzeel 2011). It consists of Core modules but also provides space to researchers to field their own questions. ODISSEI financially supports the operation of the LISS panel as well as providing small grants to researchers to field their questions at no cost. It has been in operation since October 2007 and has since conducted monthly interviews with panel members on a wide range of topics. It is an exceptionally valuable resource for the Dutch Social Science community. For example, in 2020 when the COVID-19 lockdown was implemented in the Netherlands, the LISS panel was able to provide researchers with the opportunity to field questions to a high quality panel of respondents in just three weeks (Yerkes et al. 2020; Bol 2020). The data from the LISS panel is stored in the LISS data archive³ and is accessible to verified registered users, free of charge. The LISS panel has more than 3,500 active users and has led to more than 800 peer reviewed publications. The data are documented using DDI-Lifecycle (de Bruijne and Amin 2010)⁴.

The problem of integrating LISS metadata in a single data catalogue with other surveys is well established and significant investments have been made in making the variables and questions used in LISS searchable alongside other survey data in the Netherlands. These investments resulted in a project called Survey Data Netherlands⁵ which allows researchers to conduct variable level searches across almost 700 datasets and more than 50,000 variables. However, this does not include administrative data, does not allow for semantic search and does not identify linkages between datasets.

2.3. *Problem Specification*

As part of its work, ODISSEI provides researchers with small grants to access and use CBS microdata or to field questions within the LISS panel. When researchers were applying for these grants, they faced difficulty in identifying which variables were already available in these collections. This was made all the more difficult given that the two datasets could also be linked at the individual level such that administrative data from CBS could be combined with individuals responses in the LISS panel.

³<https://www.dataarchive.lissdata.nl/>

⁴<https://ddialliance.org/node/1006>

⁵<https://www.surveydata.nl/>

The metadata from these two sources are limited in two senses. Firstly, documentation about the concepts captured by the data is only recorded at the dataset level and focuses only on the primary target concepts of the survey. Surveys can carry hundreds of variables with a vast array of concepts measured. However if only a few of these are documented at the dataset level it is a limitation. To illustrate this, we could consider a researcher who wants to study a concept amongst a particular sub-population for which a single study might not provide sufficient statistical power but where pooling individuals across studies might. In such a case the researcher would want to know all the studies that carry a particular concept. For example, if a researcher wants to investigate homophobia amongst a particular ethnic minority then nationally representative studies such as the ESS, EVS, GGS or the LISS panel might not have enough of the ethnic group to make an accurate estimate. Currently, items measuring the concept of homophobia are present in these studies but they are not included in the abstracts or dataset level metadata for each study. Instead what is needed is metadata at the variable level, including details of the concepts being captured.

Secondly, the metadata does not contain information on persistent identifiers of things like individuals or organizations that exist in multiple datasets, specifically in survey data and in administrative data. Normally, metadata catalogues don't need this functionality because individuals don't appear in two datasets. In ODISSEI however, they do due to many Dutch surveys being linkable to administrative records. If a researcher is conducting an advanced search in which they are looking for two variables which are measured for the same individual, it is necessary for the metadata to identify which survey datasets are linkable with the administrative data. In doing so, any query looking for two such variables would know two datasets can be linked.

To clarify, it is not that the metadata would contain information on whether specific individuals are included in it or whether specific individuals gave consent. The metadata simply needs to record that a common persistent identifier exists in both the survey and the administrative metadata. Then, when a researcher conducts a search for a dataset that contains multiple concepts, it is possible to see whether linkage of multiple datasets satisfies this query. For example, suppose I am looking for a dataset on 'well-being' and 'employment histories' to better understand how they affect each other. Many surveys have questions on well-being but may lack data on employment histories. Ideally such a query would return results which accounted for the possibility of linking the survey data on well-being with the administrative data on employment histories.

Similarly, if you were a researcher looking to field questions in the LISS panel you not only want to avoid asking questions in the LISS panel that have already been posed before, but also to avoid measuring concepts which could be better answered by drawing on data from the administrative records. Furthermore, if you were a researcher drafting a proposal for access to the CBS microdata it is valuable to know not only what data exists within the CBS data catalogue itself but also what data in LISS or other social surveys might be available for linkage.

If a data catalogue can't identify which datasets can be joined, then it is fundamentally limited in the ways in which it can support innovative and groundbreaking research. Researchers need to be able to traverse the full knowledge graph of metadata, to understand not only what data exists on respondents within a survey but also what data that might be linkable to within CBS. The aim of the ODISSEI Portal is therefore to incorporate the metadata of CBS microdata into a shared metadata model with the LISS panel and other social surveys and capture the linked nature of these data such that researchers can navigate the full range of data available to them.

3. Portal Design

We aim to design a portal that can integrate metadata from various data providers within ODISSEI. As outlined above, the microdata at CBS and the LISS panel data form two important data sources that we will focus on initially. However, the ODISSEI portal will be extended to contain metadata from other social science data providers involved in ODISSEI, including the European Values Study (EVS), Generation and Gender Programme (GGP), Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE), European Social Survey (ESS), Netherlands Twin Register (NTR) and the Historical Sample of the Netherlands (HSN). Moreover, many key Dutch social science datasets are currently archived in DANS-EASY, the data archive hosted by DANS, and these will also be included in the Portal (Tsoupra et al. 2018). The portal will be built to become part of the infrastructure DANS is providing to the social science community in the Netherlands.

3.1. *Dataverse*

The Portal will be based on Dataverse which is open source research data repository software developed by Harvard’s Institute for Quantitative Social Science (IQSS) (?). While the primary goal of the ODISSEI Portal is to provide metadata about social science datasets available at various sources to improve findability, the Dataverse instance will also function as an archive for long-term preservation of some of the data. In the following, we will focus on describing the collection of metadata through Dataverse.

We will use Dataverse to collect and integrate metadata from various sources. Dataverse is a widely used research data management solution that is supported by a large international community that contributes to the development and testing of the software and newly developed code. DANS has been an active member of this community for several years and has extensive experience in using Dataverse as an archiving and data management solution. DANS is the host of DataverseNL⁶, an institutional repository solution for Dutch universities and higher education organisations. Dataverse can provide a solid basis for the development of a sustainable system that enables the ODISSEI community to discover social sciences datasets available in the Netherlands and beyond.

3.2. *Metadata alignment*

An important task to make the various social science datasets discoverable is to align the metadata that are provided by each of the data providers. A lot of the social science surveys in ODISSEI, including those collected via the LISS panel, use a form of DDI to describe their data, although the exact specifications used differ. However, there are also important data providers that do not follow DDI for data documentation. Crucially, CBS is using their own internal metadata standard to describe their microdata sets. The social science datasets archived in DANS-EASY are currently described following the Dublin Core standard which only documents a basic description of the datasets production rather than an extensive documentation of its contents. The ODISSEI Portal will be harmonizing these different metadata standards by mapping them onto a central model. For this, we plan to implement the Metadata Model developed by the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA).

⁶<https://dataverse.nl/>

CESSDA encountered a similar problem of collecting and combining diverse metadata from various social science data archives for their data search portal, the CESSDA Data Catalogue. To this end, the CESSDA Metadata Model (CMM) was developed which is in use by CESSDA for various services since its release in 2019 (Borschewski et al. 2019). The CMM is based on DDI but provides a more confined list of required fields which will allow us to include metadata from a variety of sources with different levels of documentation. The model was developed by a group of experts from the CESSDA community who evaluated which metadata needs to be included to align the metadata available at various social sciences data archives and enabling the discovery of these datasets.

As ODISSEI aims to build upon existing technology and infrastructure, we are assessing the use of CMM within the Dataverse instance that will form the basis for the ODISSEI Portal. Following the guidelines established by CESSDA will later form the seamless integration of all the metadata collected in the ODISSEI Portal into the CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC). This ensures that the essential information we are collecting in the ODISSEI Portal is not only discoverable by Dutch scientists but also made available globally.

Importantly, by using Dataverse and the CMM for the ODISSEI Portal, we can build upon previous and ongoing work within the CESSDA community that is planning to use Dataverse as an archiving solution for social science data (Wittenberg et al. 2020). For instance, in the context of the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project, work has been done to integrate the CMM as well as different controlled vocabularies used by the CESSDA community into the Dataverse infrastructure.

We are currently in the process of mapping the metadata models used to document the LISS panel and the CBS microdata to the CMM. Once the mappings are made, the metadata will be imported into the Dataverse instance from which it will be searchable through a single interface. Importantly, we will also facilitate the harvesting of the metadata in the ODISSEI Portal which can be used for several purposes, including - as mentioned above - an integration into data catalogues like the CESSDA Data Catalogue. Importantly, ODISSEI partners from the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU) will be using the harvested metadata exports to enrich the available metadata and to develop more elaborate search techniques which will be explained in the following section of this paper.

3.3. *Semantic Search*

Currently, the existing search functionality in most data portals in the social sciences are limited in that the data are only indexed on the exact terms that are in the metadata (e.g. title, keywords). This means that the person who is looking up data in the portal has to be lucky enough that (s)he types exactly the words that are indexed for the data (s)he is looking for. For example, imagine a study that is indexed in Dutch, with the word "Den Haag" and a researcher is using the search functionality with the words "The Hague" or "The Netherlands". Since "The Hague" or "The Netherlands" are not part of the text, nor in the metadata, the relevant document would not show up in the search results. Hence, this 'exact match' limitation has a negative impact on the retrieval likelihood of relevant data. The search functionality fails to identify that "Den Haag" is the same as "The Hague" and would also fail to identify that "Den Haag" has a semantic relationship to "The Netherlands"/

Semantic Search is one approach to increase the retrieval likelihood of relevant data by annotating the data with elements that are part of a semantic graph. The nodes in the graph are concepts that are identified by a unique URI (which is almost identical to a URL) and represent a shared placeholder for the respective concept. One can compare it to a Wikipedia page like the one for The Hague. The page has a unique URL and gives you, among other things, information about various spelling variants, synonyms and the words for various languages. A semantic graph is basically a formal, machine-readable representation of this semantic information, containing synonyms, language variants but also properties like:

The Hague --partOf--> The Netherlands.

The Semantic Web is currently the best candidate for creating these formal graphs expressing semantic relations. The ODISSEI Portal will extend and improve search functionality by using semantic queries which will enable broader probabilistic matching and link functions over an enriched knowledge graph representation of the FAIR metadata catalogue. This incorporates the context of specific terms which are crucial in social research such as those in the European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST) (Balkan et al. 2002). By using rich and extensible data structures developed within the linked data community, ODISSEI will evolve the relatively flat metadata catalogues in use today into the highly interlinked and graph-based structures needed to conduct advanced semantic searches.

The richness in the metadata catalogue does not rely solely on the partially manual documentation and curation standards that already exist across ODISSEI associated data such as DDI. The social sciences are fortunate to have an advanced automated metadata capture system that documents the data collection process, principally through survey software such as Blaise. Besides the manual documentation and curation standards, it takes advantage of automatic and semi-automatic metadata enrichment and entity linking to enrich the available curated information. Where relevant, there will be alignment with standards used in CESSDA (CESSDA Metadata Model) at the European level and the Open Science Framework.

4. Discussion

This paper outline a problem encountered with regards to data findability in the context of ODISSEI, the dutch national infrastructure for social science. It outlined the design of the ODISSEI portal which it is hoped will solve these problems and enable semantic search of enriched metadata from a large and diverse group of data providers.

The project is however ambitious and several crucial challenges have already been identified. First, the ingestion of metadata from CBS will be problematic given that unlike metadata from social surveys, this metadata pipeline was not designed for scientific research purposes. Nor was the metadata standard developed to align with common standards used by the international scientific community. Given the central and crucial importance of CBS data to the functionality of the portal, the collaboration with CBS in its development is vital. This has been assured by CBS participation in ODISSEI and CBS experience and world leading expertise in engaging with the research community.

Secondly, the diversity of the data included in ODISSEI beyond the datasets identified here is extensive. To mitigate this challenge we have chosen to use a metadata model that is more flexible and lighter than DDI in the CMM. However, it could be

that even the CMM is not flexible enough or is too detailed for some of the data within the ODISSEI community, especially when data providers that are not traditional social surveys are considered.

Finally, the semantic search functionality will only be as good as the ontologies that it draws from. Currently, such ontologies in the social sciences are patchy, incomplete and poorly aligned across data providers. To mitigate the impact of this on the performance of the portal, ODISSEI will need to identify and communicate the use of common standards and definitions across its community of data providers.

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